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HIPPARCOS binaries: Error increase at 1 grid-period

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As noted in NDAC/LO/071, the astrometric errors seem to increase when the separation increases towards about 1 grid-period. The present note gives some further results in the (previously neglected) separation-range 1.2-2.4 arcsec.

The computations are for long-period (linear motions) binaries with equal, 8.5 mag components, and 'known' parameters (no grid search in the LS-solutions). To check for a possible influence of the scanning geometry, three different positions on the sky have been tested: at latitudes 12 (P1), 32 (P2, 'standard') and 59 (P3) degrees. Ten systems were created at each separation and position, and the rms values of the usual astrometric errors were calculated. For comparison, the rms error for the parallax only was also calculated. The results are given in Table I.

Table I. Mean (rms) astrometric and parallax errors [mas] for three different positions on the sky and separations 0.6-2.4 arcsec

Sep (")	P1		P2		P3	
	astr	par	astr	par	astr	par
0.6	1.2	1.0	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.4
0.9	1.2	1.1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5
1.2	3.2	1.1	1.4	0.6	0.8	0.5
1.5	1.1	0.6	0.9	0.6	0.6	0.3
1.8	1.2	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.6	0.3
2.1	1.1	0.8	0.7	0.9	0.8	0.6
2.4	1.2	1.0	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8

An increase of the astrometric errors is seen at 1.2 arcsec = 1 grid-period, very apparent at P1, still large at P2, and barely visible at P3. This may be qualitatively explained by comparison with the effective beam patterns given by Lindegren (1982, Strasbourg Coll.). At low latitude (P1) there are high peaks at about 1 grid-period from each star, and for equally bright components at this separation, there will be some confusion. At high latitude, this effect is much less pronounced.

Interestingly, the parallax, equal for the two stars, is not affected in the same way as the other astrometric parameters. This shows instead a minimum error around 1.5 grid-periods.